

Original Research Article

Willingness to Pay for Extension Services by Smallholder Oil Palm Farmers in Okada, Ovia North-East Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study focused on the willingness to pay for extension services by smallholder oil palm farmers in Okada, Edo State, Nigeria with the objectives of examining the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and estimating the factors affecting the likelihood of the farmers to pay for extension services. A proportionate sampling technique was adopted to select a sample size of 150 respondents from a sample frame of 300 small holder oil palm farmers from the list of registered/contact farmers in the area at 95% confidence level. A well-structured questionnaire was administered using a Contingent Valuation Method, to obtain information that formed the data collected, ranked with Likert Scale Model and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages and econometric model such as Probit model. The descriptive statistics examined the socioeconomic features which showed that majority (67%) of the farmers were aged 45-65 years and were therefore in their middle/old ages; 77% of them had 1-6 persons in their households. The Probit result reveals that age, marital status, household size, transportation cost and distance from extension service points were the factors negatively influencing the likelihood to pay for extension services, while educational level, farm size, farming experience, income, availability of extension services and extension visits increased the likelihood to pay for extension services. It was recommended that adequate funding by government and non-government agencies to research institutes be stepped up, while younger educated people should be encouraged to take to oil palm farming.

Key words: Willingness to pay, Extension services, Smallholder, Oil palm farmer

Introduction

Oil Palm belongs to the family *Arecaceae* and the genus *Elaeis* and species *guineensis*, *oleifera* etc. Oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) or the African oil palm, grow in the area that is indigenous to tropical rainforest with little savannah belt of West and western Central Africa lying between Guinea and northern Angola (11°N to 10°S) (WRM, 2001; Hardon, *et al.*, 2001). The greatest genetic variation of the crop is found in south-eastern Nigeria and western Cameroon probably because of the relatively favourable and friendly climatic factors that brought about the early domestication of the crop (Hardon, *et al.*, 2001).

The oil palm stands out as one of the important food security crops for the Nigeria mainly because of its wide usefulness (Akangbe *et al.*, 2011) and as a vehicle in the production of other crops especially by smallholder oil palm farmers based on acquired knowledge from experience and experts such as extension agents. Smallholder oil palm farmers are the major actors or major producers of oil palm in Nigeria. Nigeria is the fifth producer of palm oil globally, having about 80% of palm oil production from dispersed smallholder farmers (Solidaridad, 2020). The contributions from smallholder oil palm farmers add to the Nigeria's agricultural sector that grew from 2.12% in 2018 to 2.17% in 2020 (Abdulkareem, 2021). Abdulkareem (2021), further stated that the contributions from smallholder oil palm aggregated to 89.67% of total oil palm production in the fourth quarter of the year 2020. Smallholder oil palm farmers in Nigeria are known for their prevalent practice of intercropping to increase output using expertise and technical knowhow from extension services (Udosen *et al.*, 2005). Extension services are paramount to the creation of awareness and for the dissemination of innovation from research institutes to farmers on the latest technology to boost their output, increase profitability and enhance livelihood for sustainability.

In a quest for sustainable economic development, the Federal Government of Nigeria established the Nigerian Institute for oil palm research, (NIFOR) in 1939 with the mandate to oversee and carry out detailed research on oil palm at the Benin main station. The sole responsibility of the station is to research on the biology, ecology and economy of the crop with the aim of improving yield, increasing production for the end users through extension service delivery and providing enabling opportunities for further research. The institute has an Extension Department with the mandate of transmitting/delivering the latest technologies to smallholder oil palm farmers. Its extension agents act as mediators between the farmers and the research institute through the release of the research findings which are made available to the farmers at the grass root and facilitate farmers to identify, analyze and apply research innovations to solve impending problems relating to their farming activities for agriculture and economic development at the long run. The Extension Services include; transmission of innovation from the research institute to farmers, training on the adoption of new technologies such as hybrid tenera, and on the use of small-scale processing equipment (SSPE), release of advanced and technological cultural and management practices, accurate farming operation activities, data and calendar such as planting at the onset of the rainy season, temperature and climatic adaptation techniques like the use of organic *in situ* mulching to regulate evaporation of soil moisture, leaching and weed suppression.

They equally link the farmers with other partnerships in the business as interdisciplinary research and convey farmers' real and felt needs to the research institutes for solutions.

The extension services are carried out fortnightly to oversee, disseminate information and evaluate farmers' performances as well as the impacts of farm inputs given to the farmers. However, provision of these noble services has been thwarted by insufficient funding from government, thus compelling the research institute to request the benefiting farmers to pay for the services.

Nevertheless, it is pertinent to note that improved agricultural productivity, profitability and enhanced standard of living of farmers is achieved through extension service delivery from the products of research and development (R&D). In the absence of, or, insufficient funding from government and other agencies, sustained provision of these extension services is dependent on the willingness of these farmers to pay for the services. For efficient and effective delivery of these services, therefore, funds are required for mobility, provision of equipment like billboards, mega phones and others, security, work on experimental sites for demonstration, like the Small Plot Adoption Techniques (SPAT), advertisement in the media, engagement of town criers, equipping of training centres, amongst others.

Non-availability of the requisite funds is among the reasons for the poor ratio of 1:1189 extension agents to farmers in Nigeria as compared to the recommended ratio of 1:75 extension agents to farmers for developing countries (Agbamu, 2005).

A report has it that Nigeria has the lowest ratio of agricultural extension workers to farmers in Africa (Udegbumam, 2021). Which probably prompted the Nigerian government to announce, in March 2021, that it will hire 75,000 extension workers as part of efforts to increase food production.

This research was undertaken to examine the willingness of smallholder oil palm farmers in Okada, Ovia North-East LGA of Edo State, Nigeria to pay for extension services provided by NIFOR. It examined, among others, the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and estimated the factors influencing their willingness to pay for the extension services.

Methodology

The study was conducted in Okada, Ovia North-East local government of Edo State. Edo State is an inland state in southern Nigeria created in 1991 from the then Bendel State with its capital as Benin City. The State has eighteen local government areas split into three Agro-ecological zones; Edo North, Edo Central and Edo South (EADP, 2018), Edo South Agro-ecological zones ~~is~~ consists of seven (7) blocks namely, Oredo, Ovia south West, Ovia North East, Ikpoba-Okha, Egor, Uhunmwode and Orhionwon LGAs. The estimated population of the state was about 3,218,332 comprising 1,640,461 males and 1,577,871 females (NPC, 2006). The State lies within longitude 06' 04⁰ E and 06' 43⁰E and latitude 05' 44⁰ N and 07' 34⁰N, and has boundaries with Delta State in the south, Ondo State to the west, Kogi State to the North and part of Delta State to the east. The land mass is about 19,187 square km, and is suitable for oil palm production. Ovia North East local government area was purposively selected as a result of the presence, in the area, of the oil palm research institute (Nigerian Institute for Oil Palm Research, NIFOR) that provides and disseminates relevant research innovations to smallholder oil palm farmers, and because of the presence of a large number of small holder oil palm farmers scattered all over the area and beyond. It is also the contact point / convergent / training centre at which NIFOR Extension Agents

and all the registered / contact smallholder oil palm farmers in the State meet fortnightly. A sample size of 150 respondents was chosen using a proportionate sampling technique from a sample frame of 300 smallholder oil palm farmers from the list of registered contact farmers with NIFOR at 95% confidence level. This was done because of unequal number of farmers across the state as equal number is imperative. The formular used to arrive at the appropriate sample size, S was:

$$S = \frac{N}{1+N(e^2)} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where;

S = sample size

N = Total population of registered smallholder oil palm farmers at the contact centre in the State

e = Critical level = 5%

The Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) was used to elicit information from the farmers as its surveys set bid prices and establish if smallholder farmers will/will not pay for the services at a particular price. The information formed the data collected and was analyzed using Likert Scale Model for rating on a four point rating scale of; “Strongly Agreed, Fairly Agreed, Fairly Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed” to get the values that forms the explanatory variables. Descriptive Statistics using frequencies and percentages were used for the socioeconomic characteristics, and an Econometric Tool, the Probit Model that explains the yes/no decision by set of variables relating to small holder characteristics, services and bid prices they are willing or not willing to pay was used to evaluate willingness to pay for extension services. The socioeconomic features such as age, sex, marital status, educational level, household size, experience, farm size, annual income etc were tabled in frequencies and percentages. The values from the likert scale rating which formed the explanatory variables were fitted into the Probit model for the analysis to determine the factors influencing the willingness to pay for extension services by smallholder oil palm farmers. Probit model was chosen because of its dichotomous nature and has been used by some authors to determine the factors influencing the willingness to pay for particular goods and services (Aklilu, 2002: Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014).

The Probit model form was:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where, Y = the yes/no response for the willingness to pay,

α = intercept/constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_n$ = Coefficients of the Variables

ϵ = Error Term

X_1 = Age (years)

X_2 = Sex (Male = 1 or female= 0)

X_3 = Marital Status (dummy= 1 or 0)

- X₄ = Educational Level (No)
 X₅ = Farming Experience (years)
 X₆ = Farm Size (Ha)
 X₇ = Household Size (No)
 X₈ = Annual Income (Naira)
 X₉ = Extension Services (No)
 X₁₀ = Visits/contacts (No)
 X₁₁ = Transportation cost (Naira)
 X₁₂ = Distance (kg)

Results and Discussion

The socioeconomic features of the smallholder oil palm farmers is presented in Table 1. The result from the table shows that 67% of the farmers fell within 45-65 years of age, and so were in the middle/old age bracket, with lesser strength to carry on their daily farming activities and adopt the latest innovative practices. This is in line with the findings of Tesfahun (2014) that older people hardly adopt new technologies and are unwilling to pay for extension services. The result from sex indicated that 67% of them were males. The dominance of male oil palm farmers across the State is an indication that oil palm production in the area is a patriarchal enterprise.

Table 1: Socioeconomic Features of Small holder oil palm Farmers Willingness to pay

Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years)			Farm Size (ha)		
25 – 45	40	27	1-2	60	40
45 – 65	100	67	3-4	70	47
≥ 65	10	6	≥ 5	20	13
Total	150	100	Total	150	100
Sex			Marital Status		
Male	100	67	Single	20	13
Female	50	33	Married	130	87
Total	150	100	Total	150	100
Education Level:			Farming Experience (years)		
Non formal	30	21	< 10	20	13
Primary	40	26	10 – 20	60	40
Secondary	60	40	20 – 30	40	26
Tertiary	20	13	≥ 30	30	21
Total	150	100	Total	150	100
Household Size			Annual income		
1-3	50	32	< ₦100000	25	17
4-6	70	47	₦100000-₦200000	80	53
≥ 6	30	21	≥ ₦2000000	45	30
Total	150	100	Total	150	100
Distance			Transportation		
1-5	70	47	₦500-₦1000	20	13
6-10	50	32	₦1000- ₦2000	70	47
≥10	30	21	≥₦2000	60	40
Total	150	100	Total	150	100

Source: Field Survey Data, 2020

This implies that oil palm production is the activity performed mainly by male than female farmers in the area. This finding corroborates that of Agwu (2006) that oil palm farming was male-dominated in Abia State, as women traditionally do not own palm plantations in the area, except in households headed by women who had at least a heir. According to Mensah *et al.*, (2009), oil palm farming as a male-dominated enterprise provides an evidence of land ownership and wealth. The more oil palm stands or plantations a man has, the more the evidence of his wealth in an area. There could only be a transfer of ownership as oil palm farmland to a male inheritance. Women are not entitled to such privileges in the area because they cannot be heirs of any household or property. Acquisition of lands for oil palm plantation or farmland with wild groves is transferred from one male generation to another. However, women played a more active role in processing and marketing of oil palm produce. According to Rebecca (2016) oil palm is male-dominated because males operate mostly in the nurseries as they are more experienced, knowledgeable, accessible to extension services and have adequate time to cater for seedlings that require a lot of attention at the early stages of development. Women, on the other hand, have reproductive roles to play with little or no time and interest in the nursery activity.

The result further showed that 87% of the respondents were married. The high level of married farmers indicated that oil palm farmers in the area were responsible and likely to have large size of family labour for increase in production. Increase in number of married farmers is therefore an advantage through provision of more family labour. This is also in line with the finding of Mgbakor *et al.* (2013) that oil palm business requires a lot of human and material resources for its effectiveness, and that men, women and children are employed in various aspects of the work.

It could be seen that 66% of them had post-primary education. However, this level of education may not equip the oil palm farmers with enough managerial skills for agri-business and adoption of new technologies, as education enlightens them. This is in consonance with the findings of Adesina and Baidu-Forson (1995) that education is a major factor in the adoption and absorption of technology.

Table 1 also shows that 66% of them had 10-30 years of experience. The high farming experience among the oil palm farmers is an indication that oil palm investment is quite an old enterprise and possibly a way of life of the people WRM (2010) giving its importance as one of the main economic activities in Nigeria. In terms of farm size, 87% of the farmers planted 1-4 hectares which is within the range of smallholder farmers. The result further showed that 77% of them had household sizes of 1-6 persons. This shows that a reasonable number of family labour could be utilized if the family members actively participated in the farming activities. The annual income indicated that 53% of them earned less than ₦200,000 per annum, while 30% earn more than ₦200,000 per annum as compared to the estimated average annual output (income) of integrated smallholder oil palm farmers of 2.7 – 7.4 tons per hectare in Nigeria (Solidaridad, 2020). The result also showed that 77% of them had to cover a distance of 1-10 kilometres to access extension services. The transportation cost to points of access to extension services was ₦1,000 – ₦2,000 or more, for as much as 87% of the farmers. This high cost of transportation probably depleted available resources needed by the farmers to pay for extension services. The result from the probit model analysis is presented in Table 2. Age, marital status, household size, transportation cost and distance to extension service centres had negative and significant effects on the willingness of the

farmers to pay for extension services. On the other hand, level of education, farm size, farming experience, income, exposure to extension services and extension visits had positive and significant effects on their willingness to pay for extension services.

Table 2: Probit Model Estimates of WTP for Extension Services

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Error	Z-Value	P-Value
CONSTANT	-5.434***	-2.0230	-2.56	0.0040
AGE	-0.0336***	-0.0122	-3.05	0.0040
Sex	0.004	0.001	1.304	0.054
Marital Status	-0.681***	-0.4110	-4.58	0.0980
Educational Level	0.036***	0.019	3.23	0.057
Farming Experience	2.071**	-0.8220	2.72	0.0120
Farm Size	0.238**	-0.0941	2.53	0.0110
Household Size	-0.005***	0.002	-3.382	0.001
Annual Income	0.002***	-0.0001	7.872	0.1690
Extension Services	4.674***	0.006	2.97	0.35
Visits	0.245***	-0.0100	2.69	0.354
Transportation cost	-0.681*	-0.4110	-1.88	0.0980
Distance	-0.0458***	-0.0227	-4.58	0.0020
Number	150			
Pseudo R ²	0.666			

Source: Field Survey Data, 2020;

Significant at 1% = ***, 5% = ** and 10% = * respectively

The Probit model result of the smallholder oil palm farmers are presented in Table 2. The findings show that Age had a negative but significant effect at 1% level, implying that a one-year increase in age led to a 3.05% decrease in the willingness to pay for extension services. This indicates that the older the farmer the lesser the likelihood to pay for extension service (Gebrelibanos, 2012). The result showed that a unit increase in the number of married farmers led to a 4.58% decrease in their likelihood to pay for the extension services as opined by Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014). Also, increase in the number of household size by 1 led to a proportionate 3.382% decrease in the tendency to pay for extension services. This could be because large household sizes require more financial resources to cater for (Akinyemi *et al.*, 2014). The result revealed that any addition to transportation cost and distance to cover by either the farmers or the extension agents led to proportionate decreases of 1.88% and 4.58% respectively of the farmers' willingness to pay for the services, as most of the extension agents lacked the capacity to bear the burden of funding the services in the face of insufficient government funding. The result further revealed that increases in educational level, farming experience, extension services and visits enhanced willingness of the farmers to pay for extension services, thus confirming that knowledge is the key and a great motivator in acquisition of, and willingness to, pay for extension services. It is an indication that acquired knowledge enhanced the probability to pay. It equally showed that farmers' income was an incentive in the likelihood to pay for the services. This implies that the more the income of the farmers increase, the more likelihood they would be willing to pay for extension services (Rahji and Oloruntoba, 2009). The coefficient variation of 0.666 or 66.60% willingness to pay for extension services was not accounted for by the included explanatory variables in the model. Therefore, in a bid to enhance the likelihood to pay for extension services, educated younger

people should be involved among the smallholder farmers and there should be decrease in the number of household size. The research institutes should be well funded by government to carry out their mandates to the rural areas so as to alleviate the burden of the cost of paying for the extension services by these farmers.

Conclusion

The willingness to pay for extension services by smallholder oil palm farmers in Okada, Edo State, Nigeria was associated with some factors. This was achieved by examining the socioeconomic characteristics of the farmers and estimating the factors affecting their willing to pay for the services. The result from the socioeconomic features showed that majority (67%) of the farmers fell within 45-65 years of age, and so were in the middle/old age cadre with lesser strength. It could be seen that 66% of them had post-primary education that may have equipped them with enough managerial skills for agri-business and adoption of new technologies. The result showed that 77% of the respondents had a household sizes of 1-6 persons.

The Probit model analysis revealed that age, marital status, household size, transportation cost and distance from extension centres were the factors militating against the likelihood to pay for extension services, while education level, farm size, farming experience, income, extension services and extension visits increased the likelihood to pay for extension services. Therefore, this study recommends that for efficient and effective extension service delivery government and non-governmental agencies should fund research institutes adequately to carry out their mandates diligently as to avoid putting the burden of cost on the farmers. More educated and younger people should be encouraged to engage in smallholder oil palm farming.

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